

TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP AND JOB SATISFACTION: THE CASE OF PUBLIC INSTITUTIONS IN JORDAN

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Abstract

This study aims to discuss the impact of transformational leadership on job satisfaction among the workers of the Jordanian Public Institutions, the study mainly aimed to analyze the impact of transformational leadership on job satisfaction among the workers of the. The researcher relied on the descriptive analytical method, by referring to theoretical literature related to the subject of the current study, in addition to developing a questionnaire as a major tool to collect data from the study sample. The respondents of the study are all employees and administrators at Social Security Corporation and Vocational Training Corporation. The total population of the social security corporation is (1200) employees and (1240) employees at Vocational Training Corporation based on the human resource department of the Jordanian Prime Minister 2020. There is an impact of transformational leadership (ideal effect, motivation) on job satisfaction among the staff at level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$). the study found that the positive relationship and good treatment between managers and employees, the improvement of their performance level, the development of their skills and their appreciation contribute to increasing the levels of satisfaction among the employees and the transformational leader plays a pivotal role in shaping the values and cultures of schools, but they can only fulfill this role by showing their interpersonal and interactive skills, and from this point of view, transformational leaders in a changing world must possess the necessary skills that help them formulate values and lead change..

INTRODUCTION

The organizational exhibition and viability rely upon different things, whether formal or informal; subsequently, smallest change in the association's current circumstance can make a sensational difference, that is the reason associations need to figure out the inward powers that impact and once in a while ruin working as the most vital move towards improving and using the association overall".

Any organization can be viewed as an encased arrangement of people and tasks that cooperate to accomplish a few explicit targets. Nonetheless, there are numerous components for an association, some of them are called proper subsystems, like administration, system, innovation and targets; while different components are called casual subsystems, like authority, legislative issues, and culture (Sider, 2014).

Leadership fluctuates because of non-vital components, for example, characteristics which include: (knowledge, self-confident, and energy), abilities which include: (communication skills and social skills) or style which include: (definitive, vote based, instructing), and that implies that a similar pioneer could apply various techniques to accomplish hierarchical objectives (Van Wart, 2012; Van Slyke & Alexander, 2006). Transformational leadership concept is based on relational contract rather than on economic contract, where it takes the form of social exchange (subordinates obliged to their leaders and willing to contribute beyond the requirements of formal employment contracts), covenant contract (agreed commitment to

the welfare of both parties to the exchange) and psychological contract, which is a set of beliefs held by a person regarding the terms of exchanging agreement of which that person is a party (Rowold, 2008).

Furthermore, (Toe, et al, 2013) suggested that happy (satisfied) individuals are more motivated and hold more rigid beliefs towards an organization. Therefore, they will offer all of their efforts and do their assignments in more efficient and creative way, which will lead the organization to achieve higher quality output. Also, (Field, 2008) suggested that if organizations desire success, they should have a team of individuals who are highly satisfied with what they work, in addition to being satisfied with the work conditions and organizational environment. All the organization's components have a significant effect on the level of job satisfaction, and if one component does not fit, job satisfaction will be hindered. Therefore, it is important to understand the way these components influence job satisfaction. Accordingly, this study aimed to detect the impact of transformational leadership on job satisfaction.

Statement of the problem

Nowadays, organizations have been facing many challenges in a hyper-competitive environment and one of the problems is to find efficient employees and make them loyal; which is very challenging, where the most important asset for any organization is the individuals working in it. In this vein, employee motivation is very important for the efficiency of human resources.

This research aims to discuss the impact of transformational leadership on job satisfaction among the workers of the Jordanian Public Institutions (henceforth, JPI). Therefore, the problem statement can be cited in the following question: "Does transformational leadership influence the job satisfaction among the employees of the (J.P.I)?"

Objectives of the Study

"The study mainly aimed to analyze the impact of transformational leadership on job satisfaction among the workers of the (J.P.I). In other words, this study aimed to achieve the following objectives":

- 1) Identify the level of transformational leadership in the Jordanian Public Institutions.
- 2) Identify the level of job satisfaction among the workers of the Jordanian Public Institutions.

Research questions

The researcher is trying to answer the following questions:

- 1) What is the level of transformational leadership in the Jordanian Public Institutions ?
- 2) What is the level of job satisfaction among the workers of the Jordanian Public Institutions?

Significance of the study

"The importance of the current study is determined starting with the vitality of the liable for heading strategies", the place initiative will be a paramount work about management which serves to amplify effectiveness and attain authoritative objectives. Moreover, the study manifests the significance of the subject through work fulfillment, where work fulfillment is especially significant for each organization.

"Additionally, it is important for assessing workers' execution, accomplishing objectives and results and empowering organizations to more readily oversee change in the commercial center, including customers' needs, unofficial law and new innovation".

LITERATURE REVIEW

Transformational leadership

The world has great opportunities and even greater challenges. Businesses, institutions, and communities require that all of us should have better leadership skills. All leaders need to learn how to use power responsibly, how to apply their skills, and how to live by their values and ethics. The key to successful leadership is to recognize that each of us has the obligation to use power responsibly, constantly reinforce and apply the values and ethics that guide us and our organizations (Jong & Hartog, 2007).

Jong portrayed authority as a cycle of influencing individuals to accomplish the designated results (Lok & Crawford, 2004). Lok and Crawford recommended that initiative has a significant role in deciding the achievement or disappointment of an organization. Gill, et al recommended that pioneers help to invigorate, spur, support, and perceive their subordinates to accomplish key execution results" (Gill, et al, 2006).

Despite the fact that the past examinations about authority are classified as attribute hypotheses that are mostly centered around recognizing the characteristics, which distinguish pioneers from non-pioneers, attribute speculations propose that effective pioneers are brought into the world with certain regular characteristics, which distinguish them from their subordinates (Bryman, 2006).

To be successful, the leader should be unequivocally trusted and really dedicated to the organization and its main goal. Leaders cannot "privilege" (transformational status Hall, (Johnson, Wysocki & Kepner, 2008). Above all else, the moving motivation estimation is shaped through compartments that work with a feeling of positive thinking and a commitment to regulatory objectives and vision.

Besides, Intellectual Stimulation includes supporters in the arising new and various answers for normal intricacies and directing work in new strategies. Pioneers challenge the interaction and threaten older style suppositions, customs and cycles. Tracey and Hinkin defined Idealized Influence as a leadership that is Idealized in devotee appreciation, regard and reliance (Tracey & Hinkin, 1998).

Many leadership theories exist and one of the approaches attracting significant attention over the past several decades is transformational leadership. James Mac Gregor Burns first introduced the term transformational leadership in 1978. The term was subsequently developed by Bass, Avolio, Jung and Berson, (2003). Transformational leadership describes a leader who identifies change, develops a vision and plan of action for achieving the desired change, and executes the change with the help and commitment of group members/followers (Burns, 1978). Transformational leaders transform the self-concept of their followers by building the personal and social identity among followers with the mission and goals of the leader and organization (Shamir, House & Arthur, 1993). The followers' feelings of involvement, cohesion, commitment and performance are enhanced (Bass et al., 2003). Transformational leadership promotes followers to believe in themselves and their mission. Transformational leaders enhance the performance capacity of their followers by setting higher expectations and generating a greater willingness to address more difficult challenges (Avolio, 1999; Bass, 1998). The desired outcome of transformational leadership is dedication and enthusiasm, but not obedience and indifference (Yukl, 1989).

Transformational leadership initiative finds a way into the two highest levels of Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs, a leadership needs to make a significant degree of confidence and self-completion in their supporters to be an effectively genuine groundbreaking leadership (Convey, 2007).

Bass (1985) categorized transformational leadership initiative into four segments: (a) magnetism or individualized impact, (b) rousing inspiration, (c) scholarly incitement, and (d) individualized thought. Individualized impact alludes to how much leadership acts in worthy manners that cause subordinates to relate to the leadership.

Job satisfaction

Job satisfaction is perhaps the main sources that inspire people to remain in their work and not to leave the organization. Subsequently, job satisfaction can be used to distinguish individual's inspirations to remain or leave the organization (Price, 2001).

Furthermore, job satisfaction includes two dimensions: internal and external dimensions. Internal and external motivation has played a significance role in promoting individuals educationally and professionally. Therefore, both types of motivations have the potential of increasing the individual's job satisfaction and enhancing performance in their workplace (Hancer and George, 2003).

Job satisfaction can also be depicted in relation to what people feel about their work, and it is related to a commitment of psychological and emotional responses to the differential impression of what a person needs to get when contrasted with what the individual really gets. Additionally, it is considered as a significant component in the organizations to decide their staff reaction about their positions (Demir, 2002). Furthermore, job satisfaction has to do with the employees' evaluation of their job and their perception, while this perception is affected by unique situations, such as values, needs, and expectations (Buitendach and De Witte, 2005).

Job Satisfaction is also concerned with how the ideal things that are given to representatives bring about satisfaction; the degree of bliss during position due to accepting their arranged advantages is the specific meaning of Job Satisfaction (Rafique, et al, 2014).

"Spector (1985) suggested that there are three important features of job satisfaction. The first feature relates to human values; organizations should treat employees fairly and respectfully. Organizational assessments, which indicate high levels of job satisfaction are usually considered as a sign of the employees' good emotional and mental states" (Kumari, 2013).

The second feature refers to the behavior of workers; the employees' level of job satisfaction will affect the functioning and activities of the organization. Hence, it can be concluded that job satisfaction results in positive behavior and vice versa; dissatisfaction at work will lead to negative behaviors among workers (Kumari, 2013).

The third element or feature is identified with the worker's help of hierarchical exercises, like family day, carrying a youngster to work, or the yearly occasion party. A low laborer's interest rate or low excitement while going to these occasions could be an indication of low occupation fulfillment (Spector, 1997).

The relationships between transformational leadership and job satisfaction

"Transformational leaders are referred to as leaders who change needs, characteristics, objectives, and requirements of their disciples and prod them to beat suppositions" (Bass BM, 1995). Various experts addressed the organization between transformational leaders and leaders precisely (Riaz and Haider, 2010; Yang, 2016). "In a literature review from (1994 to 2004), Judge and Piccolo (2004) recommended that there is a strong relationship between transformational leaders and other leaders. The credits of transformational leaders proposed by Bass" (Bass BM, 1990) outfit us with a theoretical foundation for displaying employees' Job Satisfaction.

(Bogler, 2001) suggested that the practices of leaders can affect job satisfaction through the experts' impression of transformational leadership. Such leaders promote employees' presumptions with regards to their work, and they advance their work fulfillment through transformational leadership rehearses, in a case that is similar to singular thought, motivation and academic impelling. Furthermore, the powerful style depends on the interest that is practiced by leaders and gives workers the sensation of commitment. Therefore, employees are more devoted to their job tasks and have higher levels of job satisfaction.

The relationship of transformational leadership with employees' work fulfillment isn't limited to a particular progressive setting. Researchers revealed that leader's rehearses further develop employees' work satisfaction in the particular legitimate settings, including present day, informative, military, and volunteer settings (Braun S, Peus C, Weisweiler S, Frey D, 2013; Walumbwa FO, Orwa B, Wang P, Lawler JJ, 2005; Yang et al. 2011). For example, (Yang et al. 2011) suggested that the followers' positive experiences about transformational leadership among leaders achieved a prevalent distinctive verification with the affiliation, and further created camouflage of progressive goals, and more job satisfaction.

(Romero-Fernández and Chávez-Yepez, 2015) emphasized that Ecuadorian experts, as part of their work fulfillment, generally regard close and personal relationships, pay, working conditions, correspondence, and drive.

This finding was confirmed by various examinations. For example, by analyzing the level of job satisfaction among 45 workers of the Aquamare Beach Hotel in Italy, (Masouras, 2011) revealed that satisfaction is intervened by the drive bearing among employees.

(Rad et al., 2006) investigated the impact of transformational leadership on job satisfaction, legitimate obligation, and the lead of progressive citizenship. They revealed that transformational leadership earnestly influences work satisfaction.

(Barnett, Marsh, and Craven, 2005) conducted a study which revealed that instructors showed a more critical degree of satisfaction with the altered income displayed by leaders, rather than with works on identifying with a visionary head, training as a calling, and the pioneer's place as a genuine model in the consistently schedule of the school. Moreover, the results revealed that the strong relationships between the leader and educators reliably gave them more conviction; in this way, they recognized were more inclined towards identification with their boss.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study relied on the descriptive analytical method, by referring to theoretical literature related to the subject of the current study, in addition to developing a questionnaire as a major tool to collect data from the study sample.

The respondents of the current study are all employees and administrators at Social Security Corporation and Vocational Training Corporation.

The total population of the social security corporation is (1200) employees and (1240) employees at Vocational Training Corporation, (according to the human resource department of the Jordanian Prime Minister, 2020), where the reasons for choosing the respondents stem out from their knowledge and culture about the topic of this study.

Also, the researcher considered the significant information that can be collected from this population. The sample is a subset of the research community, with all the characteristics of the original community, selected in a particular way to conduct research on it and generalize its results to the entire research community.

The sample comprised (860) individual's that selected in randomly way from total of employees working in the (J.P.I), for apply the study instrument. The researcher distributed (860) questionnaires, while (672) valid questionnaires were retrieved for statistical analysis.

DISCUSSING OF THE STUDY RESULTS

The study results showed that:

1) There is an impact of transformational leadership (ideal effect, motivation) on job satisfaction among the staff at level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$)

The researcher attributes this result to the importance of transformational leadership behavior as an important pillar for effective leadership in modern organizations, and one of the main keys to success in leading groups, work teams, and building relationships that serve the goals of the organization.

This result may be logical and expected in light of the circumstances and capabilities available in (J.P.I), and although the level of job satisfaction has not risen to a high level, this result is considered positive from the researchers' point of view. The positive relationship and good treatment between managers and employees, the improvement of their performance level, the development of their skills and their appreciation contribute to increasing the levels of satisfaction among the employees.

The praise and recognition employees receive from managers, and the material support they receive in the form of rewards, directly affect their performance and level of satisfaction. In addition to that, achieving satisfaction is a necessity to achieve the goals and reach the desired results, as satisfaction greatly affects the efficiency of the individual and his/her performance of his work.

The researcher also attributes the impact of transformational leadership on job satisfaction to the fact that the transformational leader practices behaviors that make him a model and role model, and he enjoys the respect of all. It also raises in individuals a love of challenge, provides the opportunity for them to participate in the achievement of the general goals of the organization, fuels their enthusiasm, enhances the team spirit, and engages them in drawing the vision for the desired future, and it also searches individuals and encourages them to search for new creative ways and ideas to improve performance and achieve goals. Therefore, the manager who behaves according to the transformational leadership behavior is reflected on the employees, so they enjoy a higher level of satisfaction, a better civilized behavior, an awareness of clear conscience, and kindness in dealing with their colleagues and superiors.

This result may be attributed to the fact that the transformational leader plays a pivotal role in shaping the values and cultures of schools, but they can only fulfill this role by showing their interpersonal and interactive skills, and from this point of view, transformational leaders in a changing world must possess the necessary skills that help them formulate values and lead change.

This result is also attributed to the fact that job satisfaction in all its meanings is affected by the prevailing style of leadership in the organization, either positively or negatively, because the leader is directly related to the workers, there is no doubt that his style will affect the workflow and the feelings of the employees. The practical environment dominated by authoritarianism, severe control and lack of freedom will necessarily lead to pressures and a decrease in the

desire to work, which leads to low job satisfaction, and unlike the practical environment in which justice, seriousness and cooperation among the group members prevail, this will lead to the desire to work, which enhances the morale and makes Job satisfaction is high among workers.

2) There is an impact of ideal effect on job satisfaction among the staff at level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$)

The researcher attribute this result to the significant of ideal effect (charisma), which describes the behavior of the leader who is a good example for the subordinates to follow, and enjoys their admiration, appreciation and respect, and this requires participation in facing risks by the leader, and presenting the subordinates' needs and interests over his personal interests, showing an ethical highness that makes him deny himself the exploitation of his powers in the investigation personal gain. The researcher also attributes this result to the fact that the ideal effect makes the manager go beyond his personal interest in order to achieve the public good, as the manager behaves in an exemplary manner that the employees try to imitate, and the manager acts in a way through which he gains the trust, respect and appreciation of the employees, in addition to the manager's possession of the ability to persuade workers to increase their enthusiasm for work, and all of this affects the level of job satisfaction among the employees.

This result may be attributed to the fact that the ideal effect makes the manager prioritize building a set of shared values among workers, and stresses the importance of employees having a common understanding of the company's goals and mission, and behaving in an exemplary manner that most workers emulate, through his leadership skills that enhance employee confidence in his manager, and this positively affects the employees' level of job satisfaction.

3) There is an impact of motivation on job satisfaction among the staff at level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$)

The researcher attributes this result to the importance of motivation and its great role in raising the morale of the employees, considering that motivation raises in the followers a love of challenge, provides the opportunity for them to participate in the achievement of the general goals of the organization, and fuels in them enthusiasm, strengthens the team spirit, and involves them in drawing the vision for the desired future and for that a manager uses symbols, slogans and phrases of praise to direct efforts, and clarifies his high expectations from his/her followers.

This result is also attributed to the fact that motivation makes the manager direct the employees to work in a team spirit, is concerned with motivating employees to achieve the goals and vision of the company, stimulates the spirit of enthusiasm for work among workers, and encourages employees to achieve more than they expected, and this positively affects their level of job satisfaction. This result may be attributed to the great role that motivation plays by the manager to the employees through what it provides for a collective sense of administrative tasks, and informing employees about their performance level makes them feel comfortable, and raises the spirit of challenge in the hearts of the employees, all of this leads to raising the level of job satisfaction.

CONCLUSION

The past few decades have witnessed an increasing interest in the topic of leadership by scholars and thinkers in various fields, and this interest has led to the emergence of a number of modern theories that include in their content and methods characteristics and features that lead to complementarity, creativity, as well as inclusion, and dealing with the present and the future. These theories were called new leadership theories and included inspirational leadership theories, visionary leadership, and transformational leadership.

Among these modern theories that have received great attention among researchers and scholars in recent years is the theory of transformational leadership, which is the process that changes and transforms individuals. It is a leadership that seeks to raise the level of workers to achieve achievement and self-development, and promotes the process of development and development of groups and organizations, and stimulates high-minded workers, and awareness of the main issues while working to increase their self-confidence.

It is also the type of leadership that goes beyond providing incentives for the desired performance to developing and encouraging subordinates intellectually and creatively and transforming their self-interests to be an essential part of the organization's higher mission. In addition, transformational leadership uses inspiration, shared visions, and values to elevate the leader and subordinates to the highest levels of thinking and motivation, and raise morale; Leadership here prompts individuals to redouble their appropriate efforts to achieve common goals.

Transformational leadership is the one that works to expand and activate the interests of subordinates, deepen the level of awareness of these employees, and their acceptance of the vision and goals of the organization, while expanding the perceptions of employees to look beyond their own interests, for the greater good of the organization. This is achieved through more than one method, such as the charismatic view of the leader, satisfying the emotional needs of each individual and encouraging creativity for employees.

This study aimed to investigate the impact of transformational leadership on job satisfaction among the staff working at public institution in Jordan. The study results revealed that there is an impact of transformational leadership on job satisfaction, this result pointed that the leadership style plays a big role in employee satisfaction by focusing on their needs and paying attention to achieving their goals. Caring about these goals generates job satisfaction among workers and is reflected in their career lives, including a love for work and belonging to their organization and keenness to perform the tasks assigned to them seriously and sincerely, and in the event of neglecting to achieve goals for staff, they develop a behavior of dissatisfaction, loyalty and seriousness at work, and this is reflected in their behavior inside and outside the organization.

The study found that the availability of a somewhat integrated work environment affects the level of job satisfaction among workers, as the employee's feeling of the importance of the job in which he works and its great impact on individuals and society around him improves his job satisfaction level. However, the presence of some institutions that suffer greatly from a shortage

of some materials needed by the work, which makes the employee dissatisfied with the reality of the work environment due to its lack of suitability to the nature, is required for him/her, and thus this will definitely reduce the level of job satisfaction.

Finally, the researcher believes, based on the results of studies and research, that transformational leadership is an effective leadership capable of bringing about a qualitative leap in public institutions, and the manager can benefit from and employ it in order to develop employees' capabilities to the maximum, raise their level of performance, and train them to invest their energies and potential capabilities, urged them to cooperate and work in a team spirit.

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